

Priority Tasks for the Development of the Preschool Education System

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Abstract

The article describes the fundamental improvement of pre-school education institutions, the study of international best practices and the creation of a modern system in all respects. The author also gave relevant recommendations as priorities for the development of pre-school education.

Keywords: Systematic monitoring, start-up project, structure, information technology, infrastructure

Introduction

For our country, raising the young generation as well-rounded individuals is one of the most crucial tasks. This is because the prosperity of any society, its social, political, and economic well-being, depends on the intellectual and moral potential of its citizens and their spiritual development.

Indeed, solving the existing problems in nurturing the younger generation to become well-rounded individuals, ensuring the effectiveness of education and upbringing based on the demands of the times, achieving the global standard of education, and through these, forming and improving the essence and content of education, enriching the rules and laws of the preschool education system with the rich experiences of our people, and searching for its new aspects are pressing issues of today.

From this perspective, up to now, it has been crucial to radically improve the activities of preschool education institutions, increase the coverage of children of preschool age, and create a modern system in all respects by studying advanced foreign experiences.

Moreover, considering the interests and aspirations of children, providing them with thorough education and upbringing during the preschool period, expanding their worldview, developing their independent thinking abilities, instilling national and universal values in their hearts and minds to nurture them in the spirit of love for the motherland has lagged behind the demands of the times, thus requiring a revision of the preschool education management system.

How well our children perform in school and grow up with high ambitions largely depends on the education received at preschool institutions. Scientific observations and research show that a person receives 70% of all the information they acquire throughout their life during the period up to the age of five, which indicates the significance of preschool education in the development of a child's personality.

Main Part

In order to fully implement the directives given at the meeting held by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on August 16, 2017, to radically reform the preschool education system, organize the management structure of the system, and ensure 100% coverage of children aged 5-6 years in preschool education institutions, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the resolution "On the Organization of the Activities of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan." This ministry is the authorized state administrative body responsible for developing and implementing state policy in the field of preschool education. In addition, the ministry carries out its activities in accordance with the Presidential Decree No. PF-5198 dated September 30, 2017, "On Measures to Radically Improve the Preschool Education System" and the Presidential Resolution No. PQ-3305 dated September 30, 2017, "On the Organization of the Activities of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan."

In order to eliminate existing problems in reforming the preschool education system, the resolution envisions the implementation of the following extensive measures, and we will highlight some of them:

- Implementing a unified state policy aimed at the development of the preschool education system, comprehensively developing preschool education, and further enhancing the knowledge and moral-ethical level of learners;
- Introducing modern advanced forms of teaching, new pedagogical and information technologies, and effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process;
- Strengthening the material and technical base of preschool education institutions and increasing the efficiency of their activities;
- Systematically monitoring the fulfillment of state requirements in preschool education institutions;
- Developing the network of non-governmental preschool education institutions, fostering healthy competition among them, and increasing the types of educational services.

In general, preschool education, along with preparing children of various ages for school, creates the necessary organizational, methodological, psychological, and pedagogical conditions for nurturing children into healthy, well-rounded individuals, helps parents prepare children for regular schooling, and awakens an interest in learning. Preschool education is provided both at home and in state and non-state preschool institutions until the child reaches the age of 6-7 years. The goal of preschool education is to form a healthy, well-rounded child ready for school in accordance with the state requirements for preschool children's education and upbringing. In this regard, it is worth discussing the specific tasks of preschool education institutions.

Tasks of Preschool Education:

- Educating children intellectually, morally, and ethically based on the rich national cultural-historical heritage of the people and universal values;
- Instilling a sense of national pride and patriotism in children;
- Forming the need for knowledge and a desire to learn in preschool children and preparing them for a regular educational process;

- Developing children's thinking and forming skills for independently and freely expressing their thoughts;
- Ensuring the physical and mental health of children.

Preschool education institutions are established considering the demographic, socio-economic, and other characteristics of the regions. The establishment and closure of preschool education institutions are carried out in accordance with the law. Depending on their focus, preschool education institutions are divided into the following types:

- Nursery, kindergarten, nursery-kindergarten, family daycare (both as independent institutions and as branches);
- Kindergarten-school complexes;
- Preschool institutions that develop learners in one or several priority areas (such as language learning, artistic-aesthetic, sports, and other areas);
- Special preschool institutions primarily aimed at eliminating deficiencies in the physical and mental development of learners;
- Health-oriented kindergartens where sanitary-hygienic, preventive, and health-improving measures are primarily carried out;
- Mixed-type preschool institutions (where the structure may include various numbers of health-oriented groups).

Above, we have reviewed the essence and structure of the preschool education system. Now, we present our thoughts on the priority tasks for the development of the preschool education system.

One of the most important directions for the further development of preschool education today is the wide introduction of modern pedagogical and information-communication technologies into the educational process.

In recent times, comprehensive measures have been implemented to introduce the information system of preschool education management and systems for providing public services for admitting children to state preschool education institutions through State Service Centers or the Single Portal of Interactive Public Services of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan ensures the comprehensive development of learners by introducing advanced modern teaching forms, new pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process.

At the same time, the current state of preschool education demands the further development of telecommunication infrastructure, ensuring the connection of preschool education institutions to the broadband Internet network, and developing effective organizational and pedagogical forms and methods for educating a morally mature young generation.

To develop and introduce innovative processes in preschool education, the following measures are envisaged:

- Ensuring an adequate level of information security for the ministry, creating a unified information space;
- Organizing study tours to foreign countries to study, generalize, and introduce advanced international experiences in the field of preschool child development;
- Developing software tools, information databases, multimedia products in preschool education, and applying them in the activities of preschool education institutions;
- Further improving and developing the information system for managing preschool education (EMIS), creating mobile applications for data entry and rapid exchange;

- Organizing the preparation and publication of a new generation of educational and teaching-methodological literature, introducing digital educational resources, distance learning from home, and technologies for increasing parents' knowledge;
- Conducting scientific research in the field of early child development, integrating advanced scientific developments and technologies into the activities of preschool education institutions;
- Creating the necessary organizational-technical and financial-economic conditions to expand cooperation between economic entities, initiators of startup projects, scientists, financial institutions, and other interested parties for the implementation of innovation projects;
- Increasing the knowledge and skills of preschool education system staff in innovative information-communication and pedagogical technologies, organizing an innovative educational environment;
- Providing every preschool education institution in each district, initially with a reference institution, and then every preschool education institution in the republic, with personal computers connected to the Internet.

One of the foundations for providing quality preschool education is the level of training and professionalism of management and teaching staff.

In the past period, extensive work has been carried out in this direction. Specifically, the admission quotas for higher education institutions for the bachelor's program in "Preschool Education" were increased, and the study duration for this direction was reduced to three years.

On the basis of the Training and Methodological Center for Retraining and Advanced Training of Personnel of the Republic's Preschool Education Institutions, the Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Heads and Specialists of Preschool Education Institutions was established. The institute is tasked with developing knowledge and skills in modern management and pedagogical technologies among preschool education system personnel.

Another priority task for the development of the preschool education system is the development of public-private partnerships in the sector.

Solving the tasks of increasing the coverage of children with preschool education primarily requires increasing the capacity of preschool education institutions. The current volume of funding for the preschool education system, while maintaining the dynamics of population growth, ensures that the existing level of coverage of children of preschool age is maintained but does not contribute to its growth.

Considering the limitations of the State Budget funds of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the non-governmental sector should become one of the driving forces for the increase in the number of non-state preschool education institutions, and public-private partnerships should become the main mechanism for involving private entrepreneurship entities in the preschool education system. Ensuring the accessibility of preschool education, including in remote districts of the republic and places where it is challenging to expand standard forms of preschool education, can also be achieved through the introduction of new alternative forms.

One of the main tasks of preschool education institutions is to provide healthy nutrition for children, ensure their health, provide services for disease prevention, and create conditions for forming a healthy lifestyle among learners. It is worth noting here that in order to solve the tasks of providing safe and quality nutrition, such services in state preschool education institutions are partially provided to business entities on an outsourcing basis. In addition, measures are actively being implemented to improve the quality of medical services provided to children in preschool education institutions and systematically increase the qualifications of medical personnel in the preschool education system.

Another essential task is a clear goal in the process of working with families by preschool education institutions. It is advisable to conduct planned and consistent work based on forms and methods related to parents, analyzing work done in collaboration with them. There are widely practiced forms and methods of cooperation between kindergarten staff and parents and families, such as:

- Individual work with parents and families. In the educational process, this type of work is of great importance and allows for good results. The educator studies the personal characteristics of the family and the child and takes them into account in the educational process. As a result, a relationship of mutual trust, respect, and friendship is established between the educator and the parents;
- Group activities with parents. These include group and general meetings of parents, parent schools, conferences, voluntary Saturday events (practical activities of kindergarten staff with parents), question and answer evenings;
- Demonstrative activities. This type of work includes exhibitions, photo displays, showcasing children's works, open door days, parent corners, a library for parents, folders with materials on various family upbringing institutions, etc.;
- Visiting the child's family and getting to know the family members closely;
- Providing pedagogical education to parents and others.

As can be seen, finding ways to further improve the upbringing of preschool-age children at home, cooperation with parents, and strengthening the connection of family upbringing with social education are the main foundation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, organizing children's various activities based on scientifically substantiated principles ensures the proper organization of children's lives in various age groups. In our opinion, the pedagogical process aimed at ensuring the comprehensive development of children is complex and diverse. Educational issues are implemented through organizational forms of education and upbringing, various types of children's activities: teaching through classes, creative and rule-based games, independent activities, familiarization with their work and the work of adults, self-service, walks, and hygienic measures. Furthermore, the successful implementation of educational work depends on the proper organization of each type of activity in the pedagogical process in kindergarten.

References

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